

ARIES

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NOTE

Information system use cases and use context of an open reliability information system

WP6: ACCELERATOR PERFORMANCE AND NOVEL CONCEPTS (APEC)

ABSTRACT

This deliverable summarizes the use cases and the use context for an open reliability information system in the course of the H2020 research project ARIES. The deliverable contains textual and graphical documentation of use cases gathered from workshops and a comprehensive literature review. This includes the definition and description of actors and roles for the information system. The collaboration of partners from industry and academia in an international environment is considered at all stages.

ARIES Consortium, 2018

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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1 Introduction

The aim of this deliverable is to give an overview about the specific uses cases and the use context of an open reliability information system in the course of the H2020 research project ARIES. Information gathered through multiple workshops and the state of art study [1] was processed by using Enterprise Architect [2]. Textual and graphical representation of the gathered use cases were derived and are summarized in this deliverable.

The definition and description of actors and roles for the information system as well as the collaboration of partners from industry and academia in an international environment is considered at all stages. This deliverable should be the starting point for further design of the ARIES information system. The roles and use cases were defined according to international best practices and the requirements of the stakeholders.

2 Actors and Roles

This section defines the group of actors and roles in the open reliability information system. Actors describe usage categories in the system. The concept of "Actors" is used in the same sense as the concept ROLE is used in a Role Based Access Control (RBAC) context. Concrete users can get the right of one or more Actors/roles by authentication process. As depicted in Figure 1 the different actors have different notations and the role is used to identify the level of exchange like filtering of data according to the organization.

Figure 1: Actors and roles

In the following the actors and roles are described in a narrative way.

Equipment Data Provider

Equipment Data Providers deliver equipment group data or equipment unit data to the prepared Equipment Taxonomy structure. Equipment data are always associated to the organization of the Provider. The provider can classify data as:

- private (is visible only to the members of this organization),
- public (is visible to all information users).

Only members of the owning organization are allowed to update the information.

Information User

Consumes statistical information provided by the ARIS system for a single Equipment Group or a single Equipment Unit under the following restrictions:

- Raw data (event data) is only accessible by member of owning organization,
- Equipment Unit Data is only accessible by members of owning organization,
- Statistical data are only accessible, if they marked as public or if they are grouped in bigger context and there is no way to associate them to one specific company.

Quality Manager

The Quality Manager annotates data quality information to provided components. It should be able to annotate an attribute, an equipment Unit, an Equipment Group or statistical records. Different levels of confidentiality of information should be distinguished:

- in work,
- released,
- obsolete.

Different versions of data with different status can exist concurrently, but only one record is allowed with the status "released" is allowed. This is the "official" version.

Equipment Taxonomy Admin

The Equipment Taxonomy Admin is responsible for administration of the taxonomy system. They can insert or modify the terms, concepts and relations between concepts. Taxonomies will be provided for:

- building up the hierarchy of equipment classes and equipment types,
- providing description of equipment types,
- providing information for subunit and the list of maintainable units,
- providing taxonomies for environmental conditions,
- providing taxonomies for operational conditions,
- providing taxonomies for fault categories.

Reliability Data Importer

Reliability Data Importer can import event data or statistical reliability data from different sources, like logs from error logging systems or from other sources. This includes also manually collected

error events. Error events have to reference an equipment unit, which already have to exist at the time of import.

Sys Admin

General system admin. This user is responsible for general administration of security tasks and for user administration. The Sys Admin is also responsible for general administration tasks like backup, logging, auditing, etc.

Organizational Admin

Administration of the users of one specific organization.

External Actor

External actor with no login to the ARIS system, but with access to public data.

3 System boundaries

The following Figure 2 represents the system boundaries and the interaction of actors with the information system. Exemplarily shown is the interaction of the equipment data provider, the information user and the reliability data importer with the system and the interfaces to external systems e.g. the Asset & Maintenance Management Platform (InforEAM) [3] or the Accelerator Fault Tracking (AFT) [4] which could serve as a potential external data sources at CERN.

Figure 2: Information system and interaction with actors and external systems

ARIS - Accelerator Reliability Information System

ARIS - Accelerator Reliability Information System (alternative: ISAR – Information System for Accelerator Reliability). Includes all functions for administration, inserting and retrieving reliability statistic information.

AFT - Accelerator Fault Tracking

Failure data and fault tracking. Data from this system may be imported to the ARIS system.

InforEAM - Asset & Maintenance Management platform

Asset & maintenance data from InforEAM. Data from this system may be imported to the ARIS system.

4 Use Cases and Use Context

The use cases and the use context are divided in three categories of usage:

- Operational usage,
- User administration usage,
- Other administration usage.

4.1 OPERATIONAL USAGE

Describes the usage for the main purpose of the information system. This includes inserting and retrieving of data. The following Figure 3 shows the Use Cases for the Equipment Data Provider. On the one hand the actor is able to insert and edit equipment units and equipment groups and on the other hand the actor is able to change the privacy settings for these data.

Figure 3: Use Case diagram for the Equipment Data Provider

These Use Cases are described in the following section.

Insert an Equipment Unit

Equipment Units can be inserted into the reliability information system including all kinds of reliability, availability and maintainability data. The data will get the ownership of the importer. As Import format at least CSV should be supported.

Bulk insert of equipment units

A bulk list of component items should be supported to be inserted into the ARIS system. All data will get the ownership of the importers organization. As Import format at least CSV should be supported.

Bulk insert of equipment groups

A bulk list of equipment groups should be supported to be inserted into the ARIS system. All data will get the ownership of the importers organization. As Import format at least CSV should be supported.

Insert an Equipment Group

Equipment Group can be inserted into the reliability information system including all kinds of reliability, availability and maintainability data. The data will get the ownership of the importer. As Import format at least CSV should be supported.

Edit Equipment Group

After inserting equipment groups it is possible to edit its attributes and statistical information only by a member of the organization, which owns this equipment unit

Change Privacy of equipment unit or equipment groups

It is possible for the Owner (all members of the creators' organization) to change the privacy settings of an equipment unit or an equipment group.

The Use Cases of the Information User are depicted in Figure 4. The Information User is able to search for and use equipment item and equipment group data. This actor can also give feedback on the usability.

Figure 4: Use Case diagram for the Information User

Search an equipment group or an equipment unit

By the help of the taxonomy the catalogue of equipment types can be used for searching one specific equipment group or unit. For all information user the full taxonomy and the full list of equipment types is readable for lookup. Also the attributes of the equipment groups is seen public.

Uses equipment item statistic data

Statistical data for an equipment item is only visible, if the user is of the organization of the owner, or if the privacy flag of the unit is marked as "public".

Uses equipment group static data

Statistical data for an equipment group is only visible, if the user is of the organization of the owner, or if the privacy flag of the unit is marked as "public".

Uses merged equipment type statistic data

Uses equipment type statistic data means, that you merge statistic information of different equipment items and/or equipment groups.

Merging of data is allowed under following conditions:

- Equipment item data and/or equipment group data are marked as public,
- Equipment item data and/or equipment group data are of the ownership of the users organization,
- Equipment item data and/or equipment group data are marked as private, but it is not possible to identify the origin of the data in the result, because they come from more than one organization.

Gives feedback of usability

Component data can be assessed according to their usability. This feedback can influence the search characteristics for component lookup in later queries.

The Quality Manager annotates data quality information to provided components.

Figure 5: Use Case diagram for the Quality Manager

Add quality annotation for contribution

Component data can be validated according specific rules in the information system. Components of higher scores will be presented with higher priority.

At least the following status should be supported:

- unchecked raw data,
- checked raw data,
- unchecked statistical data,
- checked statistical data.

4.2 USER ADMINISTRATION USAGE

The following Figure 6 shows the Use Case diagrams for the registration and administration of actors and roles.

Figure 6: Use Case diagram for the administration of actors within the system

Authenticate to ARIS System

Login, Logout to the ARIS system.

Administration of user, organisations and roles

General administration of users, organisations and roles.

Grants and Revoke of roles for global administration

The possibility of granting or declining the access for a specific actor.

Grants local roles to organisation users

Grants local roles to organization users.

Confirms registration request

The Organisational Admin gets request from new registered users and accepts or rejects these requests.

Registration to ARIS system

Allows registration for an organisation.

4.3 OTHER ADMINISTRATION USAGE

The following Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 are showing the Use Cases for the administrative usage like importing data or administration of the structure of the taxonomy of the system.

Figure 7: Use Case diagram for the Reliability Data Importer

Figure 8: Use Case diagram for the Organizational Admin

Figure 9: Use Case diagram for the Equipment Taxonomy Admin

Import data from AFT

Import failure data from fault tracking. As Import format JSON and XML should be supported.

Import Logs from InforEAM

Asset & Maintenance data from InforEAM. As Import format JSON and XML should be supported.

Import of external handbooks and databases

For statistical calculations data from external sources like handbooks and databases are needed. This could include MIL handbooks, but also international standards.

Import Event Logs manually

It should be possible to import error logs, which came from a manually collected log. The import format should be the CSV format, the content should be defined latter.

Bulk insert of equipment units

A bulk list of component items should be supported to be inserted into the ARIS system. All data will get the ownership of the importers organization. As Import format at least CSV should be supported.

Administration of Taxonomy structure

Components are structured in a taxonomy. This admin is allowed to change fields in the hierarchy of the taxonomy and to define new component types.

5 Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable combines actors, roles and uses cases for the open reliability information system. The documentation of the Use Cases is also available in an Enterprise Architect Repository and can be made available for interested parties in the consortium.

6 References

- [1] A. Preinerstorfer, H. Humer, P. Böhm, T. Gruber, A. Niemi and J. Gutleber, Bibliography and state of the art of reliability information systems, ARIES note, (2018).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1292068>
- [2] Sparx Systems, Enterprise Architect 13: Reviewer's Guide, (2016).
<http://www.sparxsystems.com/downloads/whitepapers/EARReviewersGuide.pdf>
- [3] D. Widegren, Asset & Maintenance Management at CERN with Infor EAM, in: A&T Seminar, (CERN, 2016) <https://indico.cern.ch/event/571554/>
- [4] C. Roderick, D. Martin, S. Pade, P. Wilk and L. Burdzanowski, Accelerator Fault Tracking at CERN, in: ICALEPCS2017 Proceedings, pp. 397- 400, (JaCoW, 2018)
<https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-ICALEPCS2017-TUPHA013>